

Key indicators to measure innovation impact

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SUMMARY

Assessing the impact of collaboration within the Quadruple Helix (QH) model is essential to understanding how partnerships between academia, industry, government, and civil society drive meaningful societal, economic, and environmental change (Carayannis et al., 2018). This model fosters co-creation to tackle complex challenges (Carayannis et al., 2022), but without systematic impact assessment, it remains unclear whether these initiatives produce tangible value. Each stakeholder benefits differently from this evaluation: academic institutions can demonstrate their contributions to innovation and policy (Lina, 2022), governments can ensure the effectiveness of public investments (Paskaleva et al., 2021), industries can assess the outcomes of their partnerships (da Penha et al., 2024), and civil society can guarantee that innovation remains inclusive and ethical (González-Martínez et al., 2023; Pottaki, 2022). Beyond short-term effects, impact assessment also tracks long-term transformations, ensuring sustained progress.

Despite its importance, many existing assessment models prioritize either academic knowledge valorisation (Hladchenko, 2016; Lina, 2022; Miller et al., 2018; Nordberg, 2015) or industry-driven innovation (Appio et al., 2019; Chen & Chen, 2023; da Penha et al., 2024; Esmailzadeh et al., 2020), often neglecting the broader societal impact. Some frameworks focus on economic value, such as the ASIRPA method (Joly et al., 2015), which traces how research outputs translate into financial gains. Others emphasize civil society's role in innovation, highlighting its ability to shape regional priorities through participation (González-Martínez et al., 2023; Roman et al., 2020). For instance, the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process in Finland and Sweden (Roman et al., 2020) demonstrated how citizen involvement led to regional innovation strategies more aligned with local needs. However, few approaches holistically capture how collaboration within the QH model generates value across all stakeholder groups.

To develop a comprehensive framework, it is crucial to analyse collaboration at multiple levels. Beyond simply measuring knowledge transfer, evaluation must reflect contributions to policy development and societal well-being (Beck et al., 2022; Von Schomberg, 2024). Collaboration thrives on trust, active participation, and mutual understanding (Cai & Lattu, 2022; Carayannis et al., 2022), and assessing these aspects ensures efficient resource allocation, stronger partnerships, and long-term engagement. Moreover, a structured evaluation process supports continuous learning (Galvez et al., 2018), allowing stakeholders to refine strategies and enhance the impact of future initiatives.

Impact assessment can be conducted at three levels: micro, meso, and macro (Enjolras et al., 2021). The micro level examines individual and organizational contributions, such as skill development, knowledge exchange, and immediate benefits. The meso level explores how innovation spreads within industries or regions, influencing economic competitiveness and collaborative networks. The macro level focuses on systemic change, assessing whether innovation contributes to broader transformations like sustainability or digital transitions. While this study prioritizes the micro and meso levels due to time constraints, future research will integrate macro-level analysis to understand long-term territorial impact.

Five key dimensions are identified for impact assessment: collaboration, open science, knowledge valorisation, skills development, and innovativeness. Collaboration is evaluated through networking, communication, trust-building, and organizational structuring, ensuring that stakeholders work effectively towards shared goals (Wahdiniwaty et al., 2022). Open science is assessed based on inclusivity, transparency, reproducibility, and public engagement (Beck et al., 2022), ensuring that knowledge remains accessible and fosters trust (Powers & Hampton, 2019). Knowledge valorisation focuses on translating research into economic and societal benefits, measuring outcomes such as industry partnerships, funding acquisition, and employment opportunities (Jonkers et al., 2018; Dirkse van Schalkwyk & Steenkamp, 2024). Skills development captures the competencies gained through collaboration, including creativity, critical thinking, and leadership (Tang et al., 2020). Innovativeness examines the originality, feasibility, and societal acceptance of new solutions (Boly et al., 2014; Gabriel et al., 2023), ensuring that they address key challenges while being widely adopted. Those dimensions align and extend from existing frameworks, methodologies, and knowledge valorisation policies incorporating a more holistic and multi-stakeholder perspective essential to the Quadruple Helix model.

To facilitate effective impact assessment, this framework proposes specific indicators for each dimension, ranging from the number of interdisciplinary partnerships to technological adoption rates and social inclusion metrics. These indicators will serve as tools for evaluating innovation activities, identifying best practices, and refining collaboration processes. By applying this framework to real-world cases, stakeholders can enhance their ability to measure, manage, and optimize their joint efforts.

In the next phase of this project, a structured methodology will be developed to operationalize impact assessment within the QH model. Case studies, including innovation events, training programs, and stakeholder meetings, will validate the proposed indicators and refine the framework.

INTRODUCTION

Assessing the impact of collaborations in the QH Model is crucial as it enables stakeholders from academia, industry, government, and civil society to measure how well their collaborative efforts achieve meaningful societal, economic, and environmental change (Carayannis et al., 2018). The QH model promotes innovative co-creation that addresses complex societal challenges (Carayannis et al., 2022). However, without systematic impact assessment, it is difficult to determine whether these innovations deliver value to society or achieve their intended outcomes. Each stakeholder benefits distinctively from impact assessment. By assessing impact, academic institutions can show how their research contributes to innovation, policy development, and societal well-being (Lina, 2022). From a governmental perspective, impact assessment is essential for ensuring that public funding for research and innovation is being used effectively. Governments often invest heavily in Quadruple Helix initiatives to drive innovation and address policy priorities. Impact assessment provides a way to track whether these investments are delivering the desired results, such as improving public services, enhancing sustainability, or boosting regional development (Paskaleva et al., 2021). This accountability is important for maintaining public trust and ensuring that policies remain aligned with societal needs. For industry, impact assessment helps to evaluate whether partnerships with academia, government, and civil society are leading to tangible outcomes, such as the development of new products, services, or technologies (da Penha et al., 2024). It also allows businesses to measure their corporate social responsibility efforts, ensuring that they are contributing to societal goals and not just pursuing profit. By assessing impact, companies can improve their innovation strategies, align their activities with societal values, and build stronger relationships with other stakeholders in the innovation ecosystem. Civil society benefits from impact assessment because it ensures that innovations are inclusive, ethical, and socially responsible (González-Martinez et al., 2023, Pottaki, 2022). Impact assessment ensures that innovations are not just technologically advanced or economically profitable but are also meaningful to the communities they are intended to serve. It also promotes transparency, ensuring that the voices of citizens are heard and that innovation outcomes are aligned with public values. In addition to tracking short-term outcomes, impact assessment allows stakeholders to evaluate long-term impacts. In fact, many innovations take time to produce significant societal change, and impact assessment provides a way to measure progress over time.

However, most impact assessment models either focus highly on academia's knowledge valorisation (Hladchenko, 2016; Lina, 2022; Miller et al., 2018; Nordberg, 2015) or fully focus on the innovation or the product from the industry point of view (Appio et al., 2019; Chen & Chen, 2023; da Penha et al., 2024; Esmailzadeh et al., 2020). Nonetheless, knowledge valorisation impact assessment is important for measuring economic outcomes within the Quadruple Helix. For example, the ASIRPA method (Joly et al., 2015), illustrates how such assessments can reveal the economic value generated by public research organizations. This method was designed to analyse not only the direct outputs of research, such as patents and publications, but also the pathways through which knowledge is transformed into economic and societal benefits. In agricultural research, Impact assessment demonstrated how the research

results were integrated into innovative practices, policies, and products that benefited both industry and society. Innovations developed through collaboration in the quadruple helix ecosystem can lead to job creation, increased competitiveness, and economic growth thus enabling knowledge valorisation. Recent studies shed light upon the importance of civil society and ways to assess their participation and involvement degree in the innovation process rather than the impact of practices used for facilitating their contribution (González-Martínez et al., 2023; Roman et al., 2020). For instance, in the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (Roman et al., 2020) in Finland and Sweden, civil society's participation allowed citizens to co-create knowledge and influence regional innovation priorities. This approach ensured that innovation strategies were more aligned with local needs. Similarly, studies like González-Martínez et al. (González-Martínez et al., 2023) highlighted the importance of civil society's collaboration. Active involvement, supported by strong social and human capital, directly enhances innovation outcomes by enabling civil society to act as co-creators rather than just end users. These findings emphasize the importance of evaluating the degree of civil society's participation to foster inclusive, impactful, and sustainable innovation ecosystems without shedding light on the practices used to involve Civil Society.

Evaluating the collaboration in the QH model requires impact analysis that reflects contribution to innovation, policy development, and societal well-being beyond knowledge transfer (Beck et al., 2022; Von Schomberg, 2024). This evaluation is essential as it ensures that this complex innovation framework fosters inclusive and sustainable development. The QH ecosystem brings together academia, industry, government, and civil society, each with unique perspectives and resources. Assessing collaboration helps align these efforts effectively, ensuring that resources are used efficiently, potential gaps are addressed, and conflicts are resolved. Collaboration in the QH thrives on trust, mutual understanding, and active participation (Cai & Lattu, 2022; Carayannis et al., 2022). Evaluation ensures that all stakeholders feel valued, their contributions are recognized, and underrepresented voices are heard. It provides mechanisms to adapt to changing needs and ensures that decision-making processes are transparent and accountable (Galvez et al., 2018). This builds trust among stakeholders, strengthens partnerships, and sustains long-term engagement. By systematically evaluating collaboration, the QH framework fosters continuous learning and innovation. Identifying successful practices and areas needing improvement creates a feedback loop that enhances future initiatives. It helps organizations learn from their experiences, adopt better strategies, and adapt to emerging trends or challenges. The evaluation also measures the tangible and intangible impacts of collaboration, demonstrating how these efforts contribute to economic growth, social equity, and environmental sustainability.

Ultimately, evaluating collaboration in the Quadruple Helix is not just about measuring outcomes. It is a strategic approach to managing innovation, ensuring adaptability, maximizing impact, and driving societal transformation. The current state-of-the-art methods lack the assessment of the contribution that reflects joint efforts put together. While working on identifying best practices to improve the collaboration process and enhance co-creation and multi-disciplinary innovation environment in the QH ecosystem, impact assessment is essential in strengthening collaborations between academia, industry, government, and civil society. Impact assessment ensures the

understanding of the results of their joint efforts, while best practice evaluation provides a framework for sharing knowledge and replicating successful approaches across different sectors and communities (Epstein, 2018). For example, if an innovation hub demonstrates positive regional impacts through partnerships between universities, start-ups, and local governments, best practice evaluation would identify key success factors such as collaboration practice, open innovation and open science, innovation processes, and enhancing the relationships in their respective network. To assess the impact analysis of the collaboration in the QH ecosystem, we aim to identify the required impact indicators. This project proposes an evaluation framework that will help the Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders facilitate their knowledge valorisation and collaboration practices. Therefore, the following segments will provide a small literature review of impact indicators used to assess the quadruple helix and some case studies, then we will present the levels of impact that we aim to achieve along with the impact dimensions that will be considered. These impact aligns with and extends ongoing European Commission initiatives and established methodologies related to knowledge valorisation and impact measurement. We present existing frameworks and methodologies, ensuring that our work does not duplicate but rather complements and refines these models by incorporating a more holistic and multi-stakeholder perspective inherent to the Quadruple Helix model. Moreover, by integrating indicators that capture the broader societal and collaborative dimensions of impact, gaps in assessing co-creation dynamics and multi-sectoral innovation ecosystems are addressed. Finally, we will present the different impact indicators of each dimension.

Literature Review

Various studies demonstrate the application of these indicators across different contexts and levels of analysis, providing insights into how impact can be effectively evaluated. In regional innovation systems, universities play a significant role in driving knowledge transfer and partnerships with local businesses. Jonkers et al. (Jonkers et al., 2018) from the Joint Research Centre propose a Regional Innovation Impact Assessment framework that uses indicators such as the number of partnerships, knowledge transfer activities, graduate employment rates, and research outputs with regional impact. This approach, applied at the institutional level, supports policy decisions and performance-based funding. Impact indicators for collaboration are also embedded within the Open Innovation assessment framework. These indicators include the diversity of stakeholders involved, the number of collaborative projects, open-access publications, and societal engagement to assess knowledge co-production (Beck et al., 2022; da Penha et al., 2024).

Several studies focus more on technological innovation and firm performance highlighting the importance of innovation indicators at the firm level. In the electric vehicle sector, studies have analysed technological advancements by employing bibliometric methods to track metrics (Chen & Chen, 2023) such as the number of new patents, market penetration rates, and consumer adoption, illustrating the relevance of monitoring technological progress and its market impact. In ICT innovations, indicators include firm productivity, revenue growth, the adoption of new digital solutions, and employee digital literacy to assess the effects of technology adoption on business performance (Chege et al., 2020). This demonstrates the relevance of monitoring technological progress and its market impact. A key strength of this approach is its ability to quantitatively measure technological advancements and market reach. However, it tends to prioritize output metrics over outcomes such as societal or environmental benefits and they may neglect broader systemic and social implications of technological adoption. Additionally, Schulze et al. (Schulze et al., 2022) focused on how market orientation affects innovation performance. Their indicators covered proactive competitor orientation, technology adoption rates, and market share as critical measures, demonstrating how firm strategies shape innovation outcomes at a micro level. This micro-level analysis effectively captures firm-level strategies and their outcomes. However, it risks excluding external factors, such as policy environments and cross-sectoral interactions, which can influence innovation outcomes.

Social and eco-innovation use cases demonstrate the application of impact assessment in addressing societal and environmental challenges. One approach proposes a social innovation impact matrix (Popov et al., 2017), utilizing indicators such as social inclusion rates, participation of marginalized groups, policy influence, and improvements in community well-being to evaluate societal benefits at the regional level. This framework effectively captures social benefits at a regional level, demonstrating its strength in addressing equity and inclusion. Yet, its application may be limited by the difficulty of standardizing and measuring social impact indicators across diverse contexts. In the field of process engineering, eco-innovation research focuses on balancing environmental and economic outcomes through indicators like

reductions in energy consumption, waste management efficiency, pollution levels, and regulatory compliance, emphasizing micro-level impacts (Livotov et al., 2019). The strength of this approach lies in its alignment with sustainability goals, but it often fails to account for the long-term systemic changes required to achieve lasting environmental impact. Another study investigates the 'capacity to innovate' in agricultural systems, using metrics such as the development of new solutions, frequency of stakeholder interactions, adaptability to emerging challenges, and the integration of local knowledge, highlighting the importance of innovation capacity in enhancing resilience within agricultural communities (Allebone-Webb et al., 2016). Similarly, to explore smart city initiatives that engage public-private partnerships and citizens, indicators considered involved stakeholder engagement levels, user satisfaction, sustainability metrics, and technological adoption rates (Paskaleva et al., 2021). These projects operate at the territorial level, emphasizing the regional impact of urban innovations. These emphasize the importance of public-private-citizen partnerships but face challenges in ensuring that all stakeholder perspectives are adequately represented. Other frameworks such as the ASIRPA method (P.-B. Joly et al., 2015) and Reed et al.'s methodological framework (Reed et al., 2021) focus on comprehensive, context-sensitive evaluation approaches that emphasize the complexity of research impact pathways. Both frameworks highlight the importance of capturing long-term and diverse impacts while recognizing the role of heterogeneous actors and unintended outcomes. Smith and Hessels' or Joly and Mangematin frameworks align in their focus on understanding interactions between research entities and external partners, whether industrial or societal (P.-B. Joly & Mangematin, 1996; Smit & Hessels, 2021) and examine the mechanisms of collaboration and the integration of societal value into research processes. Joly and Mangematin focus more on laboratory-industry dynamics, while Smit and Hessels take a broader theoretical approach to the relationship between scientific and societal value. Those frameworks face challenges in standardization and require expertise to handle the complexity of their methodologies.

The recurring themes in these studies reveal common impact indicators across different sectors and contexts. Stakeholder engagement is a critical metric, measured by the number and diversity of participants, interaction frequency, and co-creation levels (Lina, 2022; Von Schomberg, 2024). For example, in the electric vehicle sector, engagement may refer to the partnership between battery supplier, vehicle manufacturers, and government entities to expand charging infrastructures and ensure regulatory compliance (Chen & Chen, 2023). On the other hand, in social innovation, engagement is more community-centric (Popov et al., 2017), emphasizing the inclusion of marginalized groups and participatory governance models to ensure solutions are both equitable and impactful.

Knowledge transfer and knowledge valorisation indicators track research outputs, partnerships, and graduate employment rates. For instance, in ICT innovation, knowledge transfer is exemplified by the development and dissemination of digital tools, integration of advanced technologies into businesses, and training programs to improve employee digital literacy (Livotov et al., 2019). By contrast, in eco-innovation, knowledge transfer often pertains to the diffusion of environmentally sustainable technologies, such as renewable energy systems or waste reduction strategies, which

are critical for achieving environmental and economic balance (Appio et al., 2019; Livotov et al., 2019). Technological adoption is assessed through patents filed, market penetration, and consumer adoption rates, reflecting the knowledge valorisation of the innovation (Badri Ahmadi et al., 2022; Chen & Chen, 2023) while in frugal innovation, technological adoption takes on a different form, focusing on creating cost-effective, accessible solutions for resource-constrained communities (Bhattacharjya et al., 2023). Social inclusion is evaluated through marginalized group participation and community well-being metrics, while sustainability metrics focus on energy consumption, waste management efficiency, and regulatory compliance. For instance, in social innovation projects, inclusion metrics often assess the participation of underrepresented groups, the reduction of social inequalities, and improvements in community well-being (Popov et al., 2017). However, in smart city initiatives, inclusion indicators consider citizen satisfaction, digital accessibility, and stakeholder involvement in urban planning to ensure that technological advancements serve diverse populations.

The studies highlight that impact assessment within the QH model must consider the diverse contributions of stakeholders and be adapted to different contexts. While indicators vary based on sector and level of analysis, they provide a foundation for comprehensive assessment frameworks that capture the complexity and effectiveness of innovation processes. The consistent application of these indicators across different use cases demonstrates their relevance in measuring both immediate and long-term impacts within innovation ecosystems. The following section will present the different levels of impact assessment.

Levels of impact

Micro, meso, and macro impact analysis are essential tools for assessing innovation effectiveness within the Quadruple Helix model (Enjolras et al., 2021). These levels of analysis allow stakeholders to evaluate the impact of innovation activities across different layers of society, from individual contributions to systemic societal changes (Galvez et al., 2018). The micro level focuses on the direct effects of innovation at the individual or organizational level. It examines how specific people or entities, such as researchers, employees, companies, or community groups, benefit from innovation initiatives. For example, a partnership between a university and a start-up might result in the development of a new product. Micro impact analysis would measure how this product impacts the start-up's growth, improves the skills of employees, and enhances the experience of end users. This level of analysis is crucial for understanding the immediate benefits of innovation in terms of skills development, job creation, and organizational performance.

The meso impact analysis takes a broader perspective, looking at the impact of innovation on sectors, industries, or regions. It focuses on how innovation spreads across a network of organizations and contributes to regional development or sectoral transformation. For instance, a regional government might invest in an innovation hub that brings together universities, businesses, and civil society organizations. Meso impact analysis would evaluate how this hub boosts regional economic development, improves sectoral competitiveness, and strengthens collaborative networks. This level of analysis is essential for understanding how innovation contributes to economic growth and regional resilience.

Finally, the macro level examines the far-reaching effects of innovation on societal systems and global challenges. It evaluates whether innovation activities contribute to long-term societal transformations, such as digital transitions, sustainability goals, or social inclusion. For example, a national policy promoting green energy innovation could lead to a significant reduction in carbon emissions and a shift toward renewable energy across various sectors. Macro impact analysis would assess how these changes contribute to national policy objectives, international agreements, and global sustainability efforts. This type of analysis is critical for ensuring that innovation ecosystems address complex societal challenges and create long-term positive change.

The three levels of impact analysis are interconnected, innovations that deliver immediate benefits at the micro level can contribute to broader sectoral impacts at the meso level and ultimately drive systemic change at the macro level. These levels of analysis are particularly important for evaluating the effectiveness of collaborations, as each stakeholder group contributes to innovation in different ways and experiences the impact at various levels.

In this project, we decided to focus more on impact indicators and the effects of best practices and develop the micro and meso levels. Limited by the timeframe of this project, macro-level indicators will not be considered since they target territorial impact on long duration. However, these indicators can be integrated into future assessments to provide a broader systemic perspective to assess long term territorial impact of.

Figure 1. QH level of impact analysis

Therefore, we define the three new levels of impact analysis presented in Figure 1. The first level focuses on assessing the behaviour and engagement of individuals involved in the collaboration. This level examines the willingness of participants to contribute, exchange knowledge, and engage with diverse actors within the innovation ecosystem. It highlights how personal readiness and motivation influence the dynamics of collaboration, including the ability to work across disciplinary, institutional, and sectoral boundaries.

The second level shifts attention to the institutional impact generated by these collaborative practices. Here, the analysis captures how the actions and behaviours of individuals influence their respective organizations. It evaluates the extent to which these practices are integrated into institutional routines, policies, and strategies, thereby fostering organizational change and enhancing the institution's capacity to participate in open innovation networks.

Finally, the third level examines the broader ecosystem-level impact, focusing on how collaborative practices strengthen the network of participating institutions and stakeholders. This level assesses the collective benefits derived from the interactions across academia, industry, government, and civil society, particularly in terms of improving trust, knowledge exchange, and co-creation processes. By analysing how these practices contribute to building a more connected and resilient innovation ecosystem, this level highlights the system-wide transformations driven by the Quadruple Helix approach. The following section will present the selected dimensions for impact assessment.

Impact Dimensions

We took an interest in five dimensions of impact assessment: (1) collaboration, (2) open science, (3) knowledge valorisation, (4) skills development, and (5) innovativeness. The first dimension is collaboration. By assessing the collaboration on an individual level, we can identify means of improvements in the collaboration processes as either organizers or participants. This will allow the evaluation of best practice impact from the individual level to the ecosystem level. The second dimension is open science, which is an indicator used to assess the impact on the three different levels as it ensures that the creation, dissemination, and use of knowledge are accessible, inclusive, and transparent across the ecosystem. Assessing open science practices is crucial for fostering trust, transparency, and collaboration within the Quadruple Helix while ensuring that innovation ecosystems are inclusive, ethical, and responsive to societal needs.

Third, knowledge valorisation assessment is essential within the ecosystem because it ensures that knowledge generated through research and innovation creates tangible value for society, industry, government, and citizens and helps ensure that collaboration outcomes are transformed into broader societal, economic, and policy impacts. Fourth, skills development is essential since the QH model fosters interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration. Innovation ecosystems benefit when individuals can work across disciplinary boundaries and understand the perspectives and priorities of other stakeholders. For example, researchers need to understand market dynamics to ensure that their innovations are commercially viable, while industry leaders must understand societal challenges to develop socially responsible solutions. Skill development programs that emphasize collaborative skills, cultural competence, and innovation management are essential to ensure that individuals can effectively navigate the complexities of the Quadruple Helix. The last dimension is innovativeness since innovation is the product of the collaboration in the QH model. This ensures that innovation processes and outcomes deliver value to all four key stakeholder groups. The Quadruple Helix framework emphasizes the co-creation of knowledge and innovation, involving diverse actors to solve societal challenges, enhance economic growth, and promote sustainable development. Innovation assessment helps track the progress and relevance of these innovation activities across the entire ecosystem.

The following sections will present respectively the different key indicators of each dimension.

1. Collaboration Dimension

Collaboration is a key factor in the success of research and innovation projects, particularly within the Quadruple Helix model (Wahdiniwaty et al., 2022). To assess the effectiveness of collaboration, various indicators can be used to measure the impact of networking, structuring, communication, and trust-building activities. Below is a detailed description of the collaboration impacts and corresponding indicators that help evaluate how well stakeholders are working together to achieve common goals.

Table 1. Collaboration indicators

Impact	Indicator
Networking	Finding new partners
	Meet and exchange with experts
	Interact with experts from different domains and different structures
	Exchange contact
	Maintaining relationships
Structuring and preparation	Tools Preparation, Structuring, Explicit Management
	Providing clear agendas
	The problem was clearly stated (availability of documentation, availability of representative, documentation about the technologies used by the problem provider, and available technologies on the market)
	Evaluation criteria were defined
	The presence of mentors/ facilitators to guide interactions
Communication	Interactions
	Idea exchange
	Exchange for guidance
	Exchange and interactions for decision-making
Build Trust	Satisfaction
	Recommendation
	Recurrence in collaboration

The first impact considered in table 1 is Networking (Feroli, 2010; Patel et al., 2012). This impact refers to the process of establishing and maintaining professional relationships that contribute to the success of collaborative projects (Beck et al., 2022). This impact can be measured through indicators such as the ability to find new partners, meet and exchange ideas with experts, and establish useful contacts. Additionally, the ability to maintain relationships over time is a critical factor that ensures long-term collaboration and continued knowledge exchange. Networking impacts are particularly important for fostering interdisciplinary partnerships and expanding the reach of research activities.

Structuring and preparation measure the organizational aspects of collaboration (Patel et al., 2012), which ensure that interactions between stakeholders are well-organized and productive. Indicators in this area include the preparation of tools and frameworks that facilitate collaboration, providing clear agendas to ensure efficient meetings, and explicitly managing interactions to avoid confusion. The presence of thorough documentation about the problem, technologies in use, and market solutions is crucial for clear communication. Furthermore, the definition of evaluation criteria helps set measurable goals for the project. The availability of mentors or facilitators to guide the collaboration process ensures that interactions are focused and purposeful.

Communication is another crucial impact of collaboration that assesses how effectively stakeholders interact, exchange ideas, and make decisions. Indicators for this impact include the frequency and quality of interactions, the exchange of ideas, and the

provision of guidance during discussions (Iqbal et al., 2018). Effective communication ensures that all stakeholders are well-informed and able to contribute meaningfully to the decision-making process. It also fosters creativity and innovation by encouraging the sharing of diverse perspectives and solutions.

Building trust is a key outcome of successful collaboration (Camargo et al., 2021; Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Unlike other indicators focused on individual-level impact, building trust is an impact at the network level over a long period. Trust is essential for fostering long-term partnerships and ensuring that stakeholders remain committed to collaborative projects. Indicators of trust-building include stakeholder satisfaction with the collaboration process, their willingness to recommend the collaboration to others, and the recurrence of collaborations with the same partners. Trust is often built over time through positive experiences, clear communication, and the fulfillment of mutual expectations.

2. Open Science Dimension

Open science impacts can be assessed using a range of indicators that measure the effectiveness of practices such as collaboration, transparency, reproducibility, and knowledge transfer (Beck et al., 2022). Below is a detailed description of the key impacts of open science and the indicators that help evaluate them within research ecosystems. The following table presents the key impacts and indicator related to Open science assessment.

Table 2. Open Science impact indicators

Impact	Indicator
Inclusivity	Number of interdisciplinary collaborations
	Citizen science projects
	Open datasets
Transparency	Open-access publications
	Preprints
	Open peer reviews
Reproducibility	Research with reproducibility packages
	Independent replications
	Applicability
Innovation and Economic Growth	Spin-offs
	Patents
	Revenue from open science
	Industry partnerships
Enhance Knowledge Transfer	Knowledge transfer workshops
	Creation and usage of open educational resources and digital learning tools
	Advancement in scientific research methodologies
	Growth in interdisciplinary research driven by cross-sectoral collaborations
	Policy briefs
	Policy references,,

Enhanced Policy and Decision-Making	Advisory roles
	Use of open datasets in policy
Public Engagement and Trust	Citizen science participants
	Public attendance at events
	Assessment of trust
Open Policy	Open-access mandates
	Policy workshops
	Open science strategies

The first impact considered in our work for open science is inclusivity, fostering interdisciplinary research and ensuring that various stakeholders, including civil society, participate in the knowledge-creation process (Robson et al., 2021). This impact is measured through the number of interdisciplinary collaborations established, citizen science projects launched, and the availability of open datasets. These indicators demonstrate the extent to which open science practices break down silos and promote inclusivity by engaging diverse groups in research activities.

The second impact is transparency, a principle of open science (Powers & Hampton, 2019), ensuring that research processes and outcomes are accessible and clear to all stakeholders. Indicators for transparency include the number of open-access publications, preprints, and open peer reviews. These practices ensure that research findings are disseminated widely and that the process of scientific validation is open and accountable. Transparency fosters trust in science and ensures that knowledge is shared without barriers.

Reproducibility is essential for ensuring the reliability and applicability of scientific research (Powers & Hampton, 2019). It is assessed through indicators such as the number of research projects that provide reproducibility packages (e.g., datasets, code), the number of independent replications of published studies, and the applicability of findings in various contexts. Ensuring reproducibility helps strengthen the credibility of research and enhances its impact by allowing others to verify and build upon existing work.

Innovation and economic growth measure the extent to which open science contributes to new products, services, and economic opportunities (Surya et al., 2021). Indicators in this area include the number of spin-offs or start-ups created based on open science outputs, patents filed, revenue generated from commercialized research, and partnerships with industry (Steiner, 2014). These indicators demonstrate how open science fuels innovation ecosystems and contributes to economic development.

Enhancing knowledge transfer refers to the movement of research outputs from academic institutions to other sectors of the ecosystem (Steiner, 2014). This impact is measured through indicators such as the number of knowledge transfer workshops organized, policy briefs produced, and the downloads or access metrics for open outputs (Bacon et al., 2019). Effective knowledge transfer ensures that research findings are translated into practical applications and inform decision-making across various domains.

Enhanced policy and decision-making evaluate the influence of open science on governance and public policy (Cole et al., 2024). Indicators include the number of

policy documents that reference open science outputs, the involvement of researchers in advisory roles, and the use of open datasets in policymaking processes, as emphasized by the European Alliance CHARM-EU (Vijge & Triyanti, 2022). These indicators highlight how open science contributes to evidence-based policymaking and improves public sector innovation.

Public engagement and trust are crucial for the success of open science initiatives. This impact is measured by the number of participants in citizen science projects, public attendance at outreach events, and survey results on trust in science and research institutions (Cole et al., 2024). These indicators reflect the extent to which open science practices are fostering public involvement in scientific processes and building trust between researchers and the public (Vijge & Triyanti, 2022).

Open policy assesses the development and implementation of policies that promote open science practices (Oliveira Jr et al., 2022). Indicators include the number of institutions adopting open-access mandates, the creation of open science strategies, and the organization of policy workshops. These measures reflect the progress made in embedding open science principles in institutional and governmental policies, ensuring that open science becomes a standard practice.

3. Knowledge Valorisation Dimension

Knowledge valorisation involves transforming research outputs into valuable contributions to society, industry, and government. The impact of this process can be measured through several indicators that capture value creation, public engagement, employment outcomes, research impact, and communication efforts. Below, Table 3 is a detailed description of these key areas of knowledge valorisation and the corresponding indicators used to assess them.

Table 3. Knowledge valorisation impact indicators

Impact	Indicator
Value Creation (Investments and funding)	Number of new industrial or governmental projects (PhDs, internships, postdocs, consultancies...)
	Industrial R&D funding
	Region/ Government R&D funding
	Non R&D funding
	Number of patents filed or granted.
	Royalty income from licensed technologies
Public engagement	Number of spin-off companies or start-ups created
	Number of participants
	Number of declined participants
Headhunting and Employment After Graduation	Interest in the knowledge learned
	Number of students getting internships with the participating entities
Research Impact	Number of employment of graduates in participating entities
	Number of publications based on collaboration projects

Promoting collaboration on Social media platforms	Number of communications regarding collaboration on different platforms
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Value creation is a fundamental measure of knowledge valorisation, reflecting how research outputs attract funding and investments from both the public and private sectors (Dirkse van Schalkwyk & Steenkamp, 2024; Jonkers et al., 2018). This impact is assessed through the number of new industrial or governmental projects initiated, such as PhDs, internships, postdoctoral research, or consultancy agreements. It also includes the level of industrial R&D funding, regional or governmental R&D funding, and non-R&D funding secured. The number of patents filed or granted, royalty income from licensed technologies, and the creation of spin-off companies or start-ups also serve as indicators of the economic value generated by knowledge transfer activities. Public engagement measures the level of interest and involvement of various stakeholders in knowledge dissemination activities (Pottaki, 2022, Vijge & Triyanti, 2022). This impact is assessed by tracking the number of participants attending knowledge valorisation events, as well as the number of declined participants. Additionally, the interest shown by participants in the knowledge learned during these engagements is a critical indicator of how effectively research outputs are being communicated to and absorbed by the public.

Headhunting and employment after graduation highlight the impact of knowledge valorisation on career outcomes for students involved in research activities (Jonkers et al., 2018). This impact is assessed by tracking the number of students who secure internships with participating entities and the number of graduates who gain employment within these entities. These indicators demonstrate the effectiveness of research collaborations in enhancing students' employability and building stronger ties between academia and industry.

Research impact is another essential dimension of knowledge valorisation, measured by the number of publications resulting from collaborative research projects. These publications showcase the successful transfer of knowledge between academic institutions and their external partners, contributing to the advancement of scientific knowledge and its practical applications.

Promoting and communicating collaboration on social media platforms is also an important aspect of knowledge valorisation (Pottaki, 2022; Shin et al., 2023). The number of communications regarding collaboration efforts on various social media platforms reflects the visibility and reach of research partnerships. Effective communication ensures that the value of collaborative projects is widely recognized and that stakeholders remain engaged with the outcomes of research initiatives.

4. Skill Development Dimension

Skill development impacts focus on the acquisition and enhancement of key competencies that contribute to personal and professional growth in various innovation ecosystems (Tang et al., 2020). Assessing these impacts through corresponding indicators allows for a deeper understanding of how individuals improve their capabilities and how these skills influence project outcomes. Below, in Table 4, is a

detailed description of each skill development impact and the indicators used to measure them.

Table 4. Skill Development Impact Indicators

Impact	Indicator
Innovation Process and Methodology	Experience co-creation, Experience Agile method, Experience the process of innovation
Learned Knowledge	Use skills and share knowledge, Technology watch, Learned application of theory
Creativity	Generation of new ideas, Application of design thinking, Creative problem-solving
Critical Thinking	Experience strategic decision making, Analysis and evaluation of complex issues
Communication	Exchange information and collaborate, Presentation skills, Writing reports and documentation
Collaboration and Teamwork	Collaboration and teamwork, Conflict resolution, Stakeholder engagement
Problem-Solving	Identification of challenges, Proposing solutions, Implementing solutions
Adaptability	Ability to adjust to new situations, Handling unexpected issues, Resilience in dynamic environments
Leadership Development	Guiding teams, Influencing decisions, Supporting the development of others
Technology Watch	Monitoring trends, Identifying new technologies, Sharing insights within the team
Reaction during Collaboration/ Training	Reactivity, Interaction, Satisfaction, engagement in discussion, use of examples based on experience and activity
Reproducibility/ Reimplementation, Change of behavior	Confidence in applying the knowledge learned in personnel activity and assessment of behavior changes

The first impact is experiencing the Innovation Process and Methodology reflecting an individual's experience with co-creation and collaborative innovation processes. It includes exposure to Agile methods and participation in iterative innovation cycles. Learned Knowledge measures the ability to acquire and use new information effectively. It includes the application of theoretical knowledge to practical tasks, technology watch activities, and knowledge-sharing with peers. Indicators such as the use of skills in real-world contexts, participation in technology watch activities, and the ability to share knowledge with others demonstrate how individuals retain and apply new information.

Creativity assesses an individual's ability to generate new ideas and solve problems through innovative approaches. Indicators include the generation of novel solutions, the application of design thinking techniques, and creative problem-solving in various situations. These indicators measure how effectively individuals can think outside the box and adapt existing ideas to create new value.

Critical Thinking involves the ability to evaluate complex issues and make strategic decisions. Indicators such as experience in strategic decision-making and analysis of complex problems measure how well individuals can assess situations, weigh options,

and determine the best course of action (Collective Council, 2018). These indicators are essential for leadership and problem-solving roles.

Communication is a vital impact that measures an individual's ability to exchange information, present ideas clearly, and document findings effectively. Indicators include participation in collaborative discussions, presentation skills, and the ability to produce clear, well-structured reports (Vijge & Triyanti, 2022). These skills are critical for ensuring that ideas are understood and implemented effectively within teams and organizations.

Collaboration and Teamwork assess an individual's ability to work well with others, resolve conflicts, and engage stakeholders in the innovation process. Indicators such as teamwork, conflict resolution, and stakeholder engagement measure the effectiveness of collaboration within diverse teams (Collective Council, 2018). These indicators show how well individuals contribute to group dynamics and foster positive working relationships.

Problem-solving evaluates how individuals identify challenges, propose viable solutions, and implement changes. Indicators include the identification of issues, solution development, and the execution of problem-solving strategies (Collective Council, 2018). These skills are essential for addressing obstacles and ensuring the success of projects in dynamic environments.

Adaptability measures an individual's ability to adjust to new situations and handle unexpected issues. Indicators such as resilience in dynamic environments, handling unforeseen challenges, and adjusting to new requirements show how well individuals can navigate change and maintain productivity in evolving contexts.

Leadership Development reflects the ability to guide teams, influence decisions, and support the professional growth of others. Indicators include leading teams, contributing to decision-making processes, and mentoring others (Tang et al., 2020). These indicators demonstrate an individual's capability to take on leadership roles and drive team success.

Technology Watch assesses an individual's ability to monitor emerging trends, identify relevant technologies, and share insights with their team. Indicators such as trend monitoring, identifying new technologies, and sharing knowledge demonstrate how individuals stay updated with industry advancements and contribute to innovation processes.

Reaction during Collaboration/Training measures engagement and interaction during collaborative activities or training sessions. Indicators such as reactivity, interaction, satisfaction, and engagement in discussions show how individuals respond to training and contribute to collaborative environments (Koppes, 2014). This impact highlights the importance of active participation in knowledge-sharing activities.

Reproducibility or ability to implement and change the behaviour assesses an individual's confidence in applying the knowledge they've learned and how their behaviour changes as a result. Indicators include the confidence to implement newly acquired skills in professional activities and observable behaviour changes over time (Koppes, 2014; T.Jeyagowri & Raja, 2007). These indicators demonstrate the practical impact of training and learning experiences on individuals' performance.

5. Innovativeness Dimension

Innovativeness refers to the capacity of a project, product, or process to introduce new ideas, concepts, or solutions that improve upon existing practices and address societal and environmental challenges (Boly et al., 2014). Measuring innovativeness requires assessing various aspects, including feasibility, originality, social approval, and the impact of engaged innovation. Table 5 presents a detailed description of these key impacts and their corresponding indicators.

Table 3. Innovativeness Impact Indicators

Impact	Indicator
Feasibility and Completion	prototyping and testing
Newness	Originality (Rarity, Ingenuity, Scope)
	Paradigm Shift
Social Approval / Acceptability	Cultural Acceptability
Engaged innovation	Social Indicators (improves quality of life, addresses societal challenges, promotes inclusivity, aims for better access to resources, services, and opportunities)
	Environmental Indicators (Reduction in carbon footprints via electric vehicles and sustainable energy sources, Decrease in plastic waste through biodegradable materials and recycling technologies, or Restoration of ecosystems through innovations in reforestation and biodiversity preservation)

Feasibility and completion measure the practicality and execution of innovative ideas. This impact is assessed through prototyping and testing activities, which ensure that innovative concepts are transformed into tangible solutions (Khan & Khan, 2018). The completion of prototypes and their successful testing demonstrate that innovations are not just theoretical ideas but feasible projects with practical applications. These indicators help assess whether innovations can be efficiently developed, deployed, and scaled to achieve their intended outcomes.

Newness captures the degree of originality and ingenuity in an innovation (Gabriel et al., 2023). This impact is evaluated through indicators such as originality, which assesses how rare and unique the solution is, and its scope, which reflects the range of areas it addresses. The presence of a paradigm shift indicates a fundamental change in how a problem is understood or addressed, showcasing the transformative potential of the innovation (Gabriel et al., 2016). These indicators help measure whether innovation introduces entirely new concepts or significantly improves existing solutions.

Social approval and acceptability focus on the cultural and societal acceptance of innovation. This impact is measured through cultural acceptability, which assesses whether the innovation aligns with societal norms and values. The more an innovation is perceived as culturally acceptable, the more likely it is to be adopted by different communities. This indicator also considers the societal readiness to integrate innovation into everyday life, which is crucial for its long-term sustainability and success.

Engaged innovation evaluates the broader impact of innovations on society and the environment (Enjolras et al., 2019). Social indicators measure whether innovation improves the quality of life, addresses societal challenges, promotes inclusivity, and ensures better access to resources, services, and opportunities. For example, an innovative healthcare solution that improves patient outcomes or a digital tool that enhances educational access would demonstrate engaged innovation. Environmental indicators assess whether the innovation contributes to sustainability by reducing carbon footprints, decreasing waste, or restoring ecosystems. Examples include innovations such as electric vehicles, biodegradable materials, and reforestation technologies, which have a positive impact on the environment and promote sustainable development.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of innovation impact within the Quadruple Helix (QH) model is essential to foster collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society. This document has provided a comprehensive framework for identifying key indicators across five core dimensions: collaboration, open science, knowledge valorisation, skills development, and innovativeness. By addressing these dimensions, we aim to measure the effectiveness of collaborative efforts and ensure that innovative ecosystems contribute to economic growth, societal well-being, and environmental sustainability. Our analysis highlights the need to assess impact at three distinct levels, micro, meso, and macro, to capture the layered nature of contributions from individual stakeholders, institutions, and networks. Existing literature and case studies reveal that the current state-of-the-art methods are often limited to specific sectors or levels of analysis, which restricts their applicability in broader, multidisciplinary innovation contexts. Therefore, this work proposes an integrated approach to impact assessment that accounts for diverse stakeholders, practices, and outcomes. The indicators presented in this document emphasize the importance of stakeholder engagement, knowledge transfer, technology adoption, societal inclusion, and sustainability. These indicators serve as tools to evaluate the success of innovation activities in achieving their intended outcomes. They also provide a framework for identifying best practices, improving collaboration processes, and ensuring that co-creation efforts yield tangible benefits across different sectors and communities. The presented approach builds upon existing methodologies such as the Regional Innovation Impact Assessment framework (Jonkers et al., 2018) of the EC and the ASIRPA method (Joly et al., 2015), ensuring that our work complements and refines these models by incorporating a multi-stakeholder perspective fundamental to the Quadruple Helix model. Moreover, by integrating indicators that capture the broader societal and collaborative dimensions of impact, such as open science, skills development, and stakeholder engagement, this framework aligns with current European knowledge valorisation policies while addressing gaps in assessing co-creation dynamics and multi-sectoral innovation ecosystems.

As a future direction, this coordination and support project will focus on developing a detailed methodology for conducting impact assessments in the QH ecosystem. This methodology will be complemented by the analysis of specific use cases, such as workshops, stakeholder meetings, training, and innovation events, to validate the proposed indicators and refine the assessment framework. The methodology will include guidelines for collecting and analysing data, ensuring reproducibility, and adapting the framework to various contexts and innovation challenges. In addition, future work will aim to identify key success factors in collaborative practices by focusing on the micro and meso levels of impact assessment. This approach aims to enable stakeholders to understand their joint efforts' immediate and intermediate effects and how they contribute to broader societal and systemic transformations. Specific use cases will illustrate how the proposed indicators can be applied in real-world scenarios, providing practical insights for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners.

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